

Governance for Data Collection, Sharing, and Use in Smart Cities in China: New Initiatives in Facilitating Innovation while Addressing Privacy and Security Concerns in Shenzhen

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Abstract

Data governance is a critical section in the construction of smart cities. Current research still has gaps in the overall data governance mechanism, particularly how data openness promotes innovation in detail and potential data security and privacy risks. Taking Shenzhen, China, as a case, this paper aims to explore collecting, sharing, using, innovation, security, and privacy of data governance, focusing on analyzing how data openness promotes social innovation and how the government will deal with potential risks of data security and privacy. At the end of the article, there are some policy implications. As for institutional innovation, the Shenzhen Municipal Government is the leader in the smart city construction, issuing many documents and supporting policies to guide the data collection, sharing, and application. Meanwhile, the government encourages enterprises to co-design the smart city through general contracting, subcontracting, and government purchases. Besides, in terms of data security and privacy protection, when framing the governance system, policymakers should consider the policy feasibility, implementation scope, and the consistency of relevant policies to reduce the confusion of enterprises and the public.

Keywords – smart city; data governance; open data; data management; data security and privacy

1 Introduction

Currently, about 55% of the world's population lives in urban areas, and this proportion is expected to increase to 68% by 2050 (UN, 2018). The rapid development of urbanization

has brought about many challenges, such as population management, traffic congestion, environmental protection, and safety governance. The dilemma facing modern urban governance requires cutting-edge technologies, citizen engagement, and effective mechanisms to provide an effective solution to tackle social challenges. The smart city as an ideal development vision for urban governance began to arouse intensive discussions in the world.

However, the smart city's conceptualization is ambiguous, and there is no unified definition in the literature (Tranos & Gertner, 2012; Meijer, 2015). Most researchers agree that the application of intelligent technologies is the key characteristic of the smart city (Tan & Taeihagh, 2020). These studies emphasized that, in the smart city system, data is recorded, transmitted, and stored through the perspective layer and network layer, which are based on the Internet of Things (IoT) and other advanced technologies. Moreover, through the real-time analysis cloud-computing based platform layer, the collected data provides the decision-making basis for city managers to improve the efficiency of urban governance (Effendi, Syukri, Subiyanto, & Utdityasan, 2016; Tan & Taeihagh, 2020). Some researchers interpret the smart city from the perspective of human resources. Their studies emphasized that citizens as the core of smart cities can create public value through engaging in public governance and public policymaking in the era of the smart city (Tan & Taeihagh, 2020). Other scholars stress the concept of collaboration in the context of a smart city. These studies highlight that the governance of smart city relies on the collaborative mechanisms of several actors (Broccardo, Culasso, & Mauro, 2019). Under the paradigm of new public governance (NPG), the principle of improving policymaking and public services through collaborative governance and participatory governance has been more and more recognized. The collaborative governance network

composed of multiple stakeholders (e.g., government, enterprises, academia, non-profit organizations, and the public) plays an increasingly important role in the development of smart cities (Broccardo, Culasso, & Mauro, 2019). Most of the existing literature focuses on the application of technology-driven smart cities. Fewer researches study smart cities from the perspective of smart governance. Questions such as defining ownership, usage right, data management among multiple stakeholders during the co-construction and co-governance of smart city, how the organizational setting and regulation formulations facilitate the institutional innovation of information sharing while privacy protection in the context of the smart city remains unanswered. Solving these questions will help governments break the information silos, enhance the cross-sectoral collaboration in the government departments, and encourage social participation in public governance.

Nowadays, most countries in the world are actively involved in the construction of smart cities, among which Europe, North America, Japan, and South Korea are in a leading position. As the pioneers of the smart city 1.0, in 2004, the South Korean government launched the "UKorea" strategy, using the Internet Technologies (IT) such as wireless sensors to help Korea to become a smart society; in 2006, the Singapore government formulated the "Smart Nation" initiative and regarded it as a leading initiative in the economic and social area; in 2010, the European Union (EU) proposed intelligent Growth as one of the critical tasks in the "Europe 2020 Strategy" (Deloitte, 2019). While in the era of Smart City 2.0, the gap of urbanization between developing countries and developed countries has gradually narrowed. Asian countries, with the highest growth rate in urbanization, begun to invest heavily in smart city projects. Notably, China has become the leading country in the construction of smart cities in the world. With more than 490 smart city pilot cities, China's smart cities account for 48% of the smart cities worldwide (Deloitte, 2019). According to Deloitte's latest report, "Super Smart City 2.0", Shenzhen ranks first among all China's smart cities in the dimensions of strategy, penetration and innovation, and second in the technology basis (Deloitte, 2019). As one of the earliest cities in China to explore the construction of a smart city, Shenzhen has a complete electronic industry chain. It has established the smart city industry cluster. The critical characteristics of Shenzhen's smart city construction are "Citizens-oriented" and firmly cooperating with Shenzhen local high-tech enterprises. In the field of Big data, Internet of Things (IoT), Cloud Computing, and Artificial Intelligence (AI), there are many representative high-tech enterprises that are cooperating with Shenzhen government departments to co-construct the various government data platforms, such as Shenzhen municipal government data opening platform, Shenzhen big data resource management center, and Guangdong province data opening platform.

Current research still has gaps in how data governance is established and managed in facilitating innovation while addressing societal concerns in smart cities in China. Inspired by the great achievement of the smart city in Shenzhen, this research will focus on the research questions of how each data governance activity process, why open data can promote innovation, and how the government should do to face the challenges of data security and privacy. In more detail, this article will explore the Shenzhen's successful experience in public-private partnership (PPP) in the construction of government data platform, to prove the innovative institution of data ownership, sharing, and using, and discuss the solution between sharing and privacy of data.

2 Literature Review

This section aims to summarize the current data governance studies in smart cities, mainly involving the concept of data governance, collecting, managing, using and data innovation in an open data environment, and institutional challenges in potential data security and privacy risk. Besides, it will also review the existing research on the smart city construction in China.

2.1 Smart city and data governance

Big data is one of the foundations of smart city development in the era of information, communication, and technology (ICT). Thus, the smart city governance can be seen as data governance to some extent, including data infrastructure construction, urban data management, and platform software design (Barns, 2018). However, data governance is a comprehensive concept, and current research in this area has focused on defining it and open government data.

The Data Management Association (DAMA) (2016) defines data governance as the exercise of authority, control, and sharing decisions over data asset management, which can be seen as high-level planning and data control. Besides, other studies describe data governance as a framework or system for decision making and accountability. Data managers execute according to established models that specify who can take action with what information, and when and in what circumstances, and what methods should be used (Panian, 2010 & Niemi, 2011 & Otto, 2011). In summary, data governance is the guiding principle for managing and using data. With a clear understanding of this concept, this article will focus on the comprehensive data collection, sharing, and application mechanisms underlying the content of smart cities.

The government can engage the public in building smart cities through open data programs. Some researchers argue that big data can be used to support mutual understanding between citizens and governments, thus greatly influencing public decision-making and improving public services. In general, open Data and open Government programs promise to show the public how the government works. In turn, the government uses big data to understand citizens' behavior and analyze the advantages and disadvantages of policies (Bertot et al., 2010 & Clarke & Margetts, 2014).

Other studies have focused on the transparency of government data. Data transparency can fight corruption and make information easy to obtain and use (Ball, 2009). However, more and more people require government agencies to release data, which indicates that citizens' rights to data cities are synchronized with their distrust of the government (Bertot et al., 2010). Some studies believe that open data does not meet its advocates' expectations and increase transparency, and that open data sets cannot better clarify or improve government processes (Clarke & Margetts, 2014). Therefore, the Open Data Initiative must be part of the government's efforts to improve transparency, enhance civil rights, and promote innovation and reform in public services (Ojo et al., 2015).

2.2 Data governance mechanism

Given that data governance is the guiding principle for managing and using data, this section will focus on the comprehensive studies on data collection, sharing, application, and innovation mechanisms underlying the smart city's content. At present, most research in these fields start from the perspective of government, describe the significance of open government data, elaborate the construction of urban data-sharing platforms by different stakeholders, and analyze the effect of open data on urban innovation.

2.2.1 Data collection

When it comes to collecting the public data, the existing research mainly focuses on analyzing how the government organizes the various stakeholders, not involving the specific data collection mechanism and how to build a data platform. Conradie & Choenni (2012) consider that the public sector should play the role of a data provider, the researchers to classify data and education, and serve as a creative industry data to the user. However, Caragliu & Del (2019) believe that in addition to government agencies, the private sector, such as companies, may also become big data providers. In general, a typical smart city project involves not only local governments and large multinational companies but also has local SMEs to translate general technical solutions into local needs. Mulder (2015) believed

that releasing public data by uniting different sectors to co-creation can establish a sustainable mechanism of open data and stimulate social innovation. However, the government's open data initiative is not just about making information available, but about building more applications to enrich people's lives, and about citizens making and designing cities together.

2.2.2 Data sharing

Data sharing in smart cities is mainly completed through government statistics websites, specialized data platforms, and mobile phone applications. There is little research in this area, which focuses on the advantages and disadvantages of sharing data in various ways and make recommendations. Cegarra-navarro et al. (2012) pointed out that the key for local governments to share data lies in how they deal with the Internet, social media software, and collective systems. Lourenco (2015) evaluated the open government portals of different countries and finally concluded that although all portals provide some form of metadata for each dataset, it is less useful and often challenging to understand. Different datasets have different metadata structures, and most data websites do not have a complete listing of possible metadata fields and their descriptions.

2.2.3 Data using and innovation

There are few existing studies on data use and innovation, the main content of which is to criticize the inconvenience of data use and prove the effect of open data on change, and lack of research on how to use data and how to promote social innovation.

Conradie & Choenni (2012) believe that there are several obstacles in opening data in practice. From the user's point of view, accessing the right database and making full use of it are the significant challenges they face. The main challenges for data providers are the lack of technology to store data and knowledge about what data can be released and the economic cost. Clarke & Margetts (2014) pointed out that perhaps the most significant criticism can be made in terms of the quality and accessibility of data. Open data sets are released in raw form so that developers and analysts can manipulate the data without formatting restrictions. This also makes the data quite difficult for citizens to access.

Roy (2014) believes that open data can promote broader collective innovation. Furthermore, Jung & Park (2015) showed that open data policies promoted the proliferation of innovative products and the development of entrepreneurial industries, so they should be incorporated into the creative economy ecosystem as long-term policies. Caragliu & Del (2019) demonstrated that smart city plans could promote

scientific and technological innovation in cities through empirical research. The number of patents filed by cities with smart city policies is higher than the EU average, especially for high-tech patents. Bonina & Eaton (2020) believes that in order to use open data for innovation, an ecosystem consisting of demand-side and supply-side participants of open government data platforms must be cultivated. In this ecosystem, third-party innovators need data sets from government agencies to create services.

2.3 Challenges in data security and privacy

As for data security and privacy protection, the research mainly stays at a superficial level to explain why there are potential risks and point out related challenges. Few articles offer policy recommendations on maintaining data security and privacy, and most are studies in the field of information technology.

Kulk & Loenen (2012) indicated that information sharing might increase the chance of disclosing private and sensitive data, such as personal name, email and postal address, date of birth, geographical location, bank account number, photo, and political/private views. Trust in institutions diminishes when their data sharing creates privacy risks that can harm citizens and individuals. Elmaghraby & Losavio (2014) believe that innovation has accelerated the construction of smart cities around the world, creating new economic opportunities and posing challenges to our data and privacy security. Rosnay et al. (2014) argued that a joint technical and legal framework could be used to manage data of a different nature and address legal, cultural, and institutional issues in a cross-sectoral manner.

All stakeholders, including researchers, governments, businesses, and other organizations, understand that advanced information technology-based smart city platforms need to adopt advanced privacy protection measures and security mechanisms. According to the present challenges to Privacy and Data Security from the Smart City Data system mainly consist of Privacy avoidance policy, medium-term Privacy policy, medium-term, and Data Provenance (Dhungana et al., 2015). People's concern over Data Privacy stems from who will deal with their Data and their degree of trust from the different Data management agencies. He believes that personal information can be classified according to individual or non-personal, as well as service or regulatory purposes (Van Zoonen, 2016).

2.4 Challenges in data security and privacy

There are few studies on the construction of smart cities in China with high similarity, mainly focusing on analyzing the development status and pointing out existing problems, government data opening, and domestic and foreign experience.

Many studies aim to explore the existing problems and barriers in the construction of smart cities in China and put forward policy suggestions, particularly in opening up government data sector. On the one hand, some researchers have researched the current situation of Chinese government opening up data and analyzed the advantages and disadvantages (Zheng, 2015; Li et al., 2015; Zheng & Gao, 2015; Huang & Wang, 2016; Zhao et al., 2019; Caprotti & Liu, 2020). Some other researchers analyzed open data platforms in different parts of China and made evaluations from the aspects of development mode, service, operative experience, and data security and privacy (Cao, 2016; Zhang & Cao, 2019; Zheng et al., 2019; Li et al., 2020). On the other hand, many researchers provide Suggestions for the construction of smart cities in China by comparing the data governance of other countries (Li, 2010; Zhou, 2015; Huang, & Li, 2016; Wang, 2016; Dong, 2017; Pu et al., 2017).

Some studies have focused on data-related laws and regulations, data security, and privacy. Hu (2015) pointed out that the government needs to improve the quality of data and pay attention to protecting the personal privacy and business secrets of enterprises. Cao (2016) & Zhang et al. (2016) believe that data-related laws and regulations are not sound and lack a unified management organization and a centralized service platform. Huang & Wen (2017) pointed out that there are policy issues such as data security and privacy, data rights and interests, and user participation in Chinese government data sharing. Wen et al. (2018) believed that China should formulate personal data protection law as soon as possible.

Besides, Xu (2012) argues that the government should take the lead to actively promote the open data movement to the society to reduce the information asymmetry between the government and the public as much as possible, enhance the government transparency and enhance the level of social democratization. Hu et al. (2016) concluded that the government needs to provide privacy and data ownership solutions and implement consistent data management policies and standards. Hu (2019) pointed out that the construction of smart cities in China should be balanced with social and environmental issues to achieve sustainable development.

Other studies focus on some smart city development cases in China. Some scholars believe that the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) has become the mainstream model in China's smart city projects. Among them, the number of Internet enterprises to participate in a substantial increase (Zhou & Xu, 2017; Lin, 2017). Also, many other studies have selected a part of cities as samples for evaluation from different dimensions, among which Shenzhen ranks in the top under different mechanisms (Rao, 2017; Li et al., 2018; Shen et al., 2018; Li et al., 2019; Yao & Xia, 2020).

3 Research Questions and Methods

It can be concluded that current research still has gaps in the overall data governance mechanism, particularly how data openness promotes innovation in detail and potential data security and privacy risks in China. As Shenzhen has significant potential in the smart city fields and gained a great achievement, this paper will take Shenzhen as a case to illustrate the data collection, use, and sharing mechanism in the smart city context. The study also introduces institutional innovations and privacy protection regulations to explore the development pathway and the solutions to privacy concerns in the age of the smart city.

This study adopts qualitative research to obtain primary data through in-depth interviews with the local high-tech enterprise that participates in the smart city platform. The question covered the collection, use, and sharing methods of Shenzhen smart city. Besides, we will also use the existing secondary data such as public government documents collected from the online government information platform and the research report on the smart city from consultation companies. These data will be used to analyze the role positioning and shared cooperation of various stakeholders under the data management mechanism.

4 Data Governance in Shenzhen

Since 2010, many Chinese cities have formulated smart city construction plans to explore new models for sustainable urban development. Shenzhen benefited from the advantages of Internet technology and policy support to become one of the first pilot cities in China. It has made many achievements in smart city development, especially in the fields of smart transportation and smart security (Rao, 2017). The construction of the smart city in Shenzhen is led by the government, in which big technology enterprises play a vital role in technical support, and other stakeholders

include the public, researchers, universities, and local small and medium-sized enterprises. Through PPP, government purchases, and other forms, Shenzhen Government cooperated with Internet technology companies such as Tencent and Huawei to build urban large-scale data centers and smart city operations and management centers. It aims to create an integrated environment of open information to support urban application system integration, and cross-department and cross-field information sharing and coordination.

This part will analyze the data governance mechanism in Shenzhen in detail based on smart cities' context, from data collection to data innovation. In particular, the research will focus on institutional innovation and application innovation of data management in Shenzhen. Also, the potential risk of data security and privacy concerns will be covered.

4.1 Data collection

The Shenzhen government agencies is mainly responsible for collecting urban data. However, data is an asset, and the data collected by each public sector is different. For example, for individuals, the public security agencies, civil affairs departments, and medical authorities will have their domain related database. Besides, for enterprises, government departments will collect their business registration information, tax information, and social security information, etc. In general, all information related to city life is collected by different public sectors.

The public sector collects data mainly through self-reporting and community workers collecting door-to-door. The government authorities maintain a high degree of confidentiality over data relating to personal privacy, which is voluntarily provided by the public on informed consent. Furthermore, all the agencies and individuals have to undergo a very complex and strict approval procedures if they want to access the data. They can only get big data that does not involve personal information. Small groups fewer than 20 people are almost impossible to get. Also, those technology enterprises only help build information platforms and do not directly participate in data collection.

4.2 Data sharing and using

Data sharing in Shenzhen is the government's responsibility, mainly presenting in public data platforms, such as designated website and mobile application. The stakeholders of data sharing include other public sectors, the public, and enterprises. This section will introduce the construction, operation, and data sharing and using.

At present, the smart city data platform in Shenzhen is mainly outsourced by the government to technology enterprises. The specific forms include enterprise general contracting mode, subcontracting mode, government purchase mode. For general contracting mode, enterprises directly sign agreements with the government for the whole project, which is generally the cooperation mode for large projects. The enterprise is responsible for the project and needs to undertake most of the platform development work. However, some tasks in the project may also be subcontracted to other partners when existing technology deficiency. The advantage of this model is that the general contractor is fully responsible for the project. In case of any problem with the products delivered by the subcontractor, the government can directly hold the general contractor responsible for the project without coordinating multiple stakeholders. Secondly, subcontracting mode means that the government signs agreements with different enterprises in different sectors to complete a project. The advantage of this model is that the government can take advantage of enterprises in various fields. Still, the disadvantage is that the government needs to balance the relationship between multiple stakeholders. Thirdly, the government can purchase enterprises' products on an annual basis rather than setting up separate projects. This model is generally applicable to small open data projects, and large projects cannot take the form of government purchases.

After built the smart city platform, all the data will be delivered to operate by the government. In the early stage of platform handover, the cooperative enterprise will be responsible for technical maintenance. Once the data operation becomes stable, it will be transferred to the government, and then it will be independently operated. However, it does not rule out that the government will set up a subsidiary to run the platform. This way can ensure data confidentiality, but there is an advantage that maybe the government does not have enough maintenance technicians.

The sharing of data is responsible for government departments, but different sectors are account for different data. Some of the data are available to all the public will be displayed on government-designated websites or other software. However, some private data can only be passed between the public sector, and the evaluation process is rigorous. Now the main obstacle for data sharing is coordination between different departments. The fundamental problem lies in human interaction rather than institutional issues. Besides, data cleansing and governance is also a problem. Much of the data cannot be presented in its natural form and needs to be standardized to make it easy for users to manipulate. The city's government information center usually account for this, and the sheer volume of data slows down the open data progress.

The data users are mainly government departments who use data to maintain social order and serve the public. For financial data, for example, the public sector is mainly used for regulatory functions. Police will use the data to crack down on financial crimes. Of course, there will be personal use of the data. For example, researchers will use publicly available city-data.

4.3 Institutional Innovations of Smart City in Shenzhen

Shenzhen's informatization development has experienced long-term exploration and practice. It has always been at the forefront in institutional innovation and top-level planning in China, laying a foundation for the subsequent construction of a "people-oriented" smart city. Shenzhen informatization development has gone through four stages: information infrastructure construction (1997-2001), e-government construction (2002-2010), smart city construction (2011-2015), and new-type smart city construction (2016-present) (CETC, 2017).

4.3.1 Information Infrastructure Construction

In 1997, Shenzhen began to develop its information infrastructure and hosted the first national informatization working meeting. The meeting defined China's national informatization system for the first time and included the Internet as part of the national informatization system (CAC, 2009). The meeting was the beginning of informatization in Shenzhen. In terms of infrastructure construction, Shenzhen began to establish a unified communication network platform, develop various types of databases, and promote the network interconnection in all districts.

4.3.2 E-government Construction

In 2002, Shenzhen began to shift its focus of the information construction to e-government. Shenzhen was one of the first pilot cities for e-government services in China. The priority of Shenzhen's e-government is to combine the reform of the government review and approval system with information technology to promote the sharing of information resources and promote "people-oriented" public services. The specific measures for e-government reform include promoting and improving various online service systems for enterprises and the public (e.g., electronic security authentication exchange platform). The e-government projects in Shenzhen involves many filed of people's livelihood, such as electronic tax filing services, online business application services, and community information services (Xinhua Net, 2002). In order to improve an e-government policy and regulation system and establish an institutional e-

government mechanism, in 2006, the Shenzhen Municipal Government launched a series of e-government policy documents called "Shenzhen E-government Pilot '1+8' Documents"(Beijing International Institute of Urban Development, 2006). These policy documents provide the detailed regulations on the disclosure of government information, Government Information Resources Sharing, and Digitization of government affairs, laying a foundation for the e-government construction in Shenzhen.

4.3.3 Smart city construction

Shenzhen's investment in and emphasis on information technology build a solid foundation for constructing a smart city (LIN, 2017). However, in promoting the development of a data-driven city, Shenzhen still faces the dilemmas of "governance fragmentation, information chimneys, and information silos. " Different data systems of different government departments use different data formats, different data standards, and different data jurisdictions, leading to low administrative efficiency, and making it extremely difficult to implement collaborations within the government departments. Thus, in 2011, Shenzhen began to promote smart city construction to reshape the city's information system. Furthermore, according to the "Guidelines of Smart Shenzhen (2011-2020)", Shenzhen proposed to optimize the smart city operation mode, establishing an operation mechanism that is led by the government, co-constructed by the service operators, system integrators, and jointly participated by multiple actors such as solution providers, equipment suppliers and value-added service providers (Shenzhen Industrial and Information Technology Bureau, 2013). Ultimately, Shenzhen aims to drive smart cities towards the road of sustainable development.

Figure 1 Operation Mechanism of Smart City in China

Source: Organized by authors

Table 2 Representative Market Participants and Their Roles in Shenzhen Smart City

Services operators	System integrators	Hardware application developers	Software application developers	Third-party service providers
Telecom operators such as China Telecom, China Mobile, China Unicom	China Electronics Technology Group Corporation, Tencent	ICT equipment suppliers such as Huawei	Tencent, Ping An Technology, iFLYTEK, Kingdee	Tencent, Ping An Technology and Vanke
The operators provide government and industry customers with solutions and integrated operations of network connections, cloud platforms, and big data applications	The general contractor of the construction and operation of smart cities. Provide a complete packaged software, hardware, and solutions to customers	Based on hardware equipment, the suppliers comprehensively use emerging technologies such as AI and IoT to provide solutions and "cloud + digital" ecology	Provide professional software products and design smart city's applications	Mainly composed of Internet, financial, and real estate companies; Provide Internet portals, operating systems, or city service applications for smart cities. Some Chinese real estate companies are transforming towards service providers and operators of the smart city community

Source: Organized by authors

In 2013, Shenzhen began to implement the "Netting Project". That means government uniformly manage the information resources of 15000 grids in Shenzhen through establishing a public primary information resources database, forming a team of information collectors, creating a comprehensive information collection system, and launching a social management network (LI, HAN, & CUI, 2014).

Figure 2 The System of the "Netting Project" in Shenzhen

Source: Organized by authors

The "Netting Project" is a city information system consisting of an information collector team, an information collection system, a public information resource base, a social service management network, a community network and a decision-making analysis support system. The Shenzhen Municipal Government divides the whole city into 15,000 basic grids, matching with 15,000 information collectors for the collection, management and sharing of information in public service management. The collected information will be delivered to the information collection

system and be integrated with information from other sources. The system will dynamically collect the information of population, houses and social events, which will become part of the public information resource base. The public information resource base refers to the thematic database containing the information of population, houses and social events. There is only one information resource base in Shenzhen, which deliver the information from the city-level, district-level, street-level to the community-level government departments. The Public Security Bureau, Civil Affairs Bureau, Education Bureau and other 36 municipal departments all access to the public basic resource base to build a data integration and sharing platform. At the same time, in the "Netting Project", Shenzhen has created a social services management network and a community work network for each community to serve the citizens. The social services management network provides administrative services, public welfare services and market services, promoting the democratic elections, decision-making and public opinion surveys for community citizens, while the community work network initially realizes the online handling of social events through the triage, processing, supervision, feedback and assessment of community issues. The community network and community work network provide citizens a platform to actively participate in public affairs and improve the efficiency of public services, which support the analysis of government's policy-making. Through connecting the collected information with locations in the electronic map, the decision-making support system could play its functions of data mining and statistical analysis. Based on the results of data analysis, policy makers could match public service objects with public service resources, which could help policy makers coordinate the supply-side and demand-side of public services in a timely manner.

In the "Netting Project", the government has built a professional team to carry out data collection and management as well as refined its public management to each community in Shenzhen. Furthermore, the unified information resource platform has greatly improved the efficiency of government services. However, there are no specific regulations for owners, managers and users in the process of sharing, leading to the problem of lack of clear authority and responsibility of data governance. In this period, the information silos still existed, and the share of government information is inefficient.

In 2015, Shenzhen Municipality formally issued the "Measures of Shenzhen Municipality for the Administration of Government Information Resources Sharing" (People's Government of Shenzhen Municipality, 2015). The new measures address the ownership, management, and use of government information, providing an institutional guarantee and institutional innovation for information

sharing within the government. The new measures regulate that the government has ownership of the government information collected by different departments within the government. The collection department has the management right while other departments have the use right. Meanwhile, the new measures stress that the sharing of government information is the fundamental principle and non-sharing is the exception. Information that cannot be shared must be justified and be approved by the relevant department, which breaks the silos of government information and the sharing of information further promotes the applications and city governance through data mining and data analysis. In addition, the basic database, thematic database, and shared platform of government information in Shenzhen shall be co-constructed by different departments of the Shenzhen Municipal Government.

Although the government has launched a series of policy documents to clarify the issue of data rights in the data governance process. Still, the smart city construction lacks top-level design and overall planning. Data is scattered across different levels of government and different departments, leading to multiple hotlines and many obstacles in aggregating data. Therefore, it is difficult to adopt emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Big data to deliver high-level and high-quality services to the public.

4.3.4 New-type Smart City Construction

Traditional smart cities in China only focus on the use of new technologies to facilitate urbanization. Therefore, they lack superior design and lead to the problem of various information chimneys and silos in the city. The new-type smart city is a complex system of "holistic planning," "people-oriented," and "sharing," aiming to promote the integration of information, data and technology to achieve cross-level, cross-regional, cross-sector, cross-business, cross-platform collaborative data management and services(SUN, 2019).

In 2015, Shenzhen became one of the pilot cities of the new-type smart city. Besides universities and research institutions, more and more market participants are also involved in the superior design and holistic planning of smart cities, such as the China Electronic Technology Group Corporation that used to engage in the construction of smart applications in the past. By breaking the information chimney and promoting information integration, the government's administrative efficiency under the new-type smart city has been dramatically improved. For example, Shenzhen is the first city to process and approve specific public services to the citizens in seconds (Shenzhen Press, 2018). According to the "The Overall Plan of Shenzhen Municipal Government for new-type smart city

construction," Shenzhen will cooperate with local high-tech enterprises to establish a smart city and they plan to reach "Six One" goals by 2020, including One Picture Full Perception, One Platform for Integrated Operation and Linkage, One Number in Shenzhen, Enjoy Life with One Screen, One Key to Know the Overall Situation, and One-stop Innovation and Entrepreneurship (Deloitte, 2019). These six goals of the new-type smart city correspond to cases of government-enterprise cooperation and enterprise from different industries began to participate in the smart city ecosystem. In this period, the roles of government and enterprise change in the field of city management in Shenzhen. On one hand, the government began to transform from a service provider to a service supervisor; on the other hand, enterprises use the industry's resources to develop smart city and transfer their roles to the public service operators, further exploring the supply side of the public service market.

Compared to the internal circulation of government information in traditional smart cities, the new-type smart cities pay more attention to the convergence and integration of data resources from various sources, emphasizing the interconnection and information sharing between government and social institutions to form a centralized government Big data resource management center in the city and to provide a unified data-sharing platform for departments to carry out smart applications. Shenzhen has successively launched the "Action Plan of Shenzhen Municipal Government for promoting Big Data Development (2016-2018)" "Implementation Plan for the Construction of Shenzhen City Big Data Center." These plans provide a superior design for the development of a new-type smart city in Shenzhen, including the improvement of 6 underlying databases (e.g., population and housing databases) and the construction of 20 thematic databases (e.g., health security, education, and other livelihood fields). The Shenzhen, Big Data Resource Management Center, was also established to unify the data management of government departments at all levels, establish a unified Big data platform for government affairs, and achieve information sharing in Shenzhen (WU,2019).

Figure 3 The Model of Shenzhen New-type Smart City

Source: Shenzhen New-type Smart City Design Concept and Practice, CETC, 2017

In the era of new-type smart cities, the scope of data openness has been extended from the government to the whole society and at the same time, the economic benefits brought by the data openness are growing. However, the value of data is rarely recognized in the production activities and for enterprise participated in the smart city, their data assets are challenging to secure. This may hinder the integration of government and social data and the creation of public value.

To solve this problem, in April 2020, China issued the "Opinions of the CPC Central Committee and the State Council on Improving the Systems and Mechanisms for Market-based Allocation of Factors of Production," where data was regarded for the first time as a new factor of production equal to land, labor, capital, and technology (Xinhua News Agency, 2020).

Table 6 Measures to Facilitate the Value of Data Factor in China

Key Points	Detailed Measures
Facilitate the open and sharing of government data;	1) Share the government data to facilitate the digital governance of government and the development of Big data industry. Therefore, the government should be responsible for the data sharing, using, management and security protection mechanisms;
	2) Strengthen the top-level design and improve the shared performance appraisal mechanism to encourage all government levels to participate in the data sharing;

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3) Establish the unified data-sharing platform and use emerging techniques to process and analyze the data; 4) Clarify the specific process of sharing open data and improve the whole life cycle management specifications such as data selection, review, collection, release, and offline collection. At the same time, relevant standard rules are formulated to clearly define the overall standards, terminology standards, metadata format standards, interface specifications, platform construction standards, etc. for data openness.
<p>Improve the resource value of public data;</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Explore the data application scenarios in society. Enhance the data flow through the business application and improve the value of data. 2) Coordinate government data resources and public data resources and establish a big data platform—open themes data to the society. 3) Accelerate data legislation and solve the problem of "unwilling to share." Formulating data standards and regulations. Enhance the supervision of Internet companies with massive data resources to avoid the leaking of sensitive data.
<p>Enhance the integration of data resources and security protection.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Clarify data ownership. 2) Clarify the data pricing mechanism and measurement mechanism. 3) Enhance the market supervision mechanism. 4) Strengthen the data security protection mechanism.

Source: Organized by authors, referred to "Opinions of the CPC Central Committee and the State Council on Improving the Systems and Mechanisms for Market-based Allocation of Factors of Production."

4.4 Data Security and Privacy Protection

With the widespread application of emerging technologies such as Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data and Cloud Computing, China's smart cities are facing the explosive development of data volumes. While benefiting from the data governance, data security has aroused the extensive concerns in the whole society. Data convergency and opening increase the risk of data leaks and privacy disclosure. To tackle these challenges, China is engaging in the laws and regulations formulations for data security and privacy protection in recent years.

4.4.1 "Measures for Data Security Management (Draft for Comments) "

In 2019, the Cyberspace Administration of China issued the "Measures for Data Security Management (Draft for Comments) " (After this referred to as the Measures), which is regarded as China's "General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)". Compared to the "Cybersecurity Law of the People's Republic of China" issued in 2016, the Measures focus more on the concept of data security, providing a legal protection for personal information and important data. Before the release of the Measures, China has introduced several policy documents on the protection of personal information, such as the "Information security technology—Personal information security specification", however these policies rarely have the legal force. Thus, the Measures can be regarded as the first legal regulations on data security in China.

The Measures are applicable to both private and public sectors and individuals, including "Network operators," "Government departments," and "Personal Information Subject. " Specifically, "Network operator" refers to the owners and administrators of the network as well as network service providers while "Personal information subject" refers to the natural person identified or connected by the personal information.

Besides, the Measures clarify the definition of terms "Network data," "Personal data," and "Important data." In China, all kinds of electronic data collected, stored, transmitted, processed, and generated is defined as the "Network data."

Besides, the measures provide a definition of "Personal Information", which indicates that China is paying attention to the privacy protection of personal information. "Personal Information" refers to all kinds of information recorded in electronic or other forms, which can be used, independently or in combination with other information, to identify a natural person's identity, including but not limited to the natural person's name, date of birth, identity certificate number, biometric information, address, and telephone number. A clear definition promotes the standardized guideline for private and public sectors to protect personal privacy and data security.

The Measures have clarified provisions for the data activities such as the collection, storage, transmission, process and use of data, as well as the protection, supervision, and administration of cybersecurity. In terms of data collection, the Measures regulate the rules for the collection, use and record of data. For example, article 8 of chapter 2 provides that network operators should develop and disclose the rules for the collection and use of data. Network operators shall register in the local cybersecurity

for the record. The rules shall include the purposes, types, volume, frequency, methods, the scope of the personal information to be collected and used; the place of storage, retention period and what the network operator will do with personal data after the retention period expires; the ways and methods for the data subject to withdraw consent and to access, correct and delete personal information; and the rules to be followed when providing personal information to others. In terms of the process and use of data, the Measures highlight the protection for personal data and important data, the protection of users' consent right and timely response as well as the data security risk assessment. For example, articles 19, 20, and 23 of chapter 3 provide that network operators shall take measures to protect personal data and valuable data and delete personal data when the data exceeds the retention period or users reject the push information. And articles 21, 22, 26, and 27 stresses the protection of users' consent right and timely response when receiving reasonable requests, reports, and complaints from users. In terms of supervision and regulation of data security, the Measures clarify the responsibilities of different government departments in protecting data security. A cyberspace administration shall supervise the network operators to implement data security management obligations. The national cyberspace administration and the State Council's market regulatory department shall be responsible for the security authentications. The relevant competent departments of the State Council shall be responsible for the security protection of data provided by network operators. Additionally, network operators shall inform the users promptly when security incidents occur as well as the punishment measures such as confiscating the violator's illegal income from there, suspending relevant business operation when network operators violate the provision of the Measure or the laws.

These provisions would help private sectors and individuals that participated in the data activity in the guidance of privacy protection and data security. However, there are places for improvement in the Measures. For example, the policy maker should consider the feasibility of regulations and policies. Though the Measures innovatively propose the "Record System" to review and manage the data security mechanism of the network operators, the number of subjects and the volume of data could be very large due to the dynamic real-time data and the wide range of network operators. Besides, compared to the large fines imposed on companies under the "GDPR", the Measures implement softer penalty measures such as admonition and public expose.

4.4.2 "Regulations of Shenzhen Special Economic Zone on Data (Consultation Draft)"

As mentioned before, China has introduced the concept of data factors and proposed new management measures to data security. These measures reduce data users' concerns about privacy and data security while protecting data assets and playing the multiplier effect of data in improving productivity. With the arrival of the Big data era, the data owner has driven the intensive discussions in society. As a pioneer in the digital economy and smart city, Shenzhen has announced: "Regulations of Shenzhen Special Economic Zone on Data (Consultation Draft)" (After this referred to as the Regulations) in July 2020, which first mentioned data rights and the Shenzhen-Hong Kong-Macau data. The data right brings a new perspective in China that the digital economy should consider data security, data privacy while developing the digital industry.

Compared to the "Measures for Data Security Management (Draft for Comments)," the Regulations are more detailed in terms of data classification, data activities, and security guarantees. For example, the Regulations have detailed provisions on "Public Data", which refers to the various types of data and their secondary data collected or generated and recorded or saved in a particular form when the public management and service agencies perform their duties or provide public management and services following the law. While "Government Data" refers to various data resources collected, generated, stored, and managed when government departments at all levels and their technical support centers perform their duties according to the law. The distinction between the "Public Data" and "Government Data" indicates that as China moves from e-government and traditional smart cities to new smart cities, data resources have expanded from government information resources to diversified data such as Internet and enterprise data. Besides, internal-used government information platforms have changed into the city Big data platform that is more accessible to multiple parties.

The Regulations also have detailed provisions on data rights for the persons and the public. Specifically, Persons shall have data rights for their personal data while "Public data" is a new type of state-owned asset and its data rights belong to the state. "Data factor market participants" like data company also have the data rights of the legally collected data and the copyright of the data generated by themselves.

Meanwhile, Shenzhen proposed the data integration mechanism and data cross-border international cooperation mechanisms in Shenzhen, Hong Kong, and Macao area in the Regulations, which covers the establishment of a free economic zone for cross-border data circulation, the data white list mechanism. As the start point of China's reform

and opening up, Shenzhen will play an exemplary role in data exchange and international (regional) cooperation in the future.

Overall, the Regulations provide an innovative perspective of data rights as it clearly defines the public data and the data rights for the public data and individual data. However, there is a lack of instructions for public data categories and the definition related to personal information may be inconsistent in different policies and regulations, which may confuse enterprises and individuals in the implementation of data security management and privacy protection.

5 Conclusion

By interviewing the relevant high-tech enterprise co-constructing the Shenzhen smart cities and reviewing the government's public information and existing literature, some implications could be concluded. With a solid basis of information infrastructure and a complete government information resources sharing mechanism, Shenzhen's smart city is moving towards a sustainable development path characterized by "people-oriented," "innovation," "sharing," and "security."

Firstly, for small open data software, besides, to directly outsourcing smart city data projects to enterprises, the government can also adopt innovative modes such as organizing solicitation of software design works. This approach can not only raise the public's attention to smart cities but also promote public participation in smart city design.

Secondly, the Shenzhen Municipal Government is the leader in smart city construction. It has issued many documents and supporting policies to guide the collection, sharing, and application of data and many policy concepts such as "sharing principle" are ahead of other cities. At the same time, the government encourages enterprises to participate in the construction of smart cities through cooperation, such as "general contracting, subcontracting, and government purchase."

Third, considering the regulations on privacy protection and data security is framing in recent years. However, policymakers have started to issue relevant provisions to safeguard the privacy rights of smart city participants, and the relevant concepts are still not clear enough. Several relevant documents refer to the protection of personal-related information, but personal data is inconsistent. For example, the scope of personal information in the Measures does not mention personal credit information. Therefore,

policymakers still need a unified framework of rules to improve the mechanism standards covering technology, management, supervision, and security while formulating the regulations and laws.

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